

Impact Factor: 6.145

ISSN: 2181-0990
DOI: 10.26739/2181-0990
www.tadqiqot.uz

JRHUNR

JOURNAL OF REPRODUCTIVE HEALTH AND URO-NEPHROLOGY RESEARCH

TADQIQOT.UZ

VOLUME 4,
ISSUE 4 **2023**

МИНИСТЕРСТВО ЗДРАВООХРАНЕНИЯ
РЕСПУБЛИКИ УЗБЕКИСТАН

Журнал репродуктивного здоровья и уро-
нефрологических исследований

JOURNAL OF REPRODUCTIVE HEALTH AND URO-NEPHROLOGY RESEARCH

Главный редактор: Б.Б. НЕГМАДЖАНОВ

Учредитель:

Самаркандский государственный
медицинский университет

Tadqiqot.uz

Ежеквартальный
научно-практический
журнал

N^o 4
2023

ISSN: 2181-0990
DOI: 10.26739/2181-0990

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Page Maker | Верстка: Хуршид Мирзахмедов

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UDC: - 616.441-008.61-07-08

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FEATURES OF THE CLINICAL COURSE OF THYROTOXICOSIS SYNDROME AMONG CARDIAC PATIENTS

For citation: Khayitboeva Komila Khujayazovna. Features of the clinical course of thyrotoxicosis syndrome among cardiac patients. Journal of reproductive health and urology research 2023, vol. 4, issue 4, pp 245-250

 <http://dx.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8335629>

ABSTRACT

Introduction. Diffuse toxic goiter (DTG) is a disease that is characterized by increased production of thyroid hormones and diffuse enlargement of the thyroid gland, like all autoimmune diseases, it is more common in patients with a positive family history, and usually caused by environmental factors such as stress, smoking, infection, iodine exposure and the postpartum period, and after highly active antiretroviral therapy due to immune reconstitution, which primarily affects the thyroid gland. **Relevance.** DTG is one of the most common thyroid diseases and is the most important clinically significant thyroid pathology, occurring in 0.5-1.5% of the population. **The aim of the study** is to determine the frequency of occurrence of diffuse toxic goiter among cardiac patients and to assess its clinical course. **Materials and Methods** used in order to investigate the research were the collection of clinical materials which were gathered from the clinical research. The research was carried out within 6 months, from January to July 2022, the collection of material was carried out at the Specialized Scientific and Practical Medical Center for Cardiology and Cardiac Surgery of the Aral Sea Region. We consulted 1150 patients who were referred by cardiologists to rule out thyroid diseases. **Results and Discussion.** out of 1150 patients, 71 patients (6.2%) had diseases occurring with thyrotoxicosis syndrome. While analyzing hormonal and immunological data, DTG was diagnosed in 24 (33.8%) patients. The majority of patients were women - 70.8%. **Conclusions.** It turned out that many patients with DTG with cardiovascular pathology turn to a cardiologist at the onset of the disease (37.5% of newly diagnosed DTG).

Key words: thyrotoxicosis syndrome; among cardiac patients; diffuse toxic goiter; immunological marker; amiodarone-induced thyrotoxicosis.

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ОСОБЕННОСТИ КЛИНИЧЕСКОГО ТЕЧЕНИЯ СИНДРОМА ТИРЕОТОКСИКОЗА СРЕДИ КАРДИОЛОГИЧЕСКИХ БОЛЬНЫХ

АННОТАЦИЯ

Диффузный токсический зоб (ДТЗ) – это заболевание, которое характеризуется повышенной продукцией тиреоидных гормонов и диффузным увеличением щитовидной железы, как и все аутоиммунные заболевания, чаще встречается у пациентов с положительным семейным анамнезом, это вызвано факторами окружающей среды, такими как стресс, курение, инфекция, воздействие йода и послеродовой период, а также после высокоактивной антиретровирусной терапии из-за восстановления иммунитета, которое, в первую очередь, поражает щитовидную железу. Целью исследования является определение частоты встречаемости диффузно – токсического зоба среди кардиологических больных и оценить его особенности клинического течения. Материалы и методы. Сбор клинического материала было проведено в течение 6 месяцев, в период от января до июля 2022 года, сбор материала был проведен в Специализированном научно-практическом медицинском центре кардиологии и кардиохирургии региона Приаралья. Нами было проконсультировано 1150 пациентов, которые были направлены кардиологами с целью исключения заболеваний щитовидной железы. Результаты. Из 1150 пациентов, у 71 пациента (6,2%) были выявлены заболевания, протекающие с синдромом тиреотоксикоза. При анализе гормональных и иммунологических данных было выявлено у 24 (33,8%) больных диагностирован ДТЗ. Большинство больных составляют женщины - 70,8%. Выводы. Выяснилось, что многие пациенты с ДТЗ с сердечно-сосудистой патологией, в дебюте заболевания обращаются к кардиологу (37,5% впервые выявленный ДТЗ).

Ключевые слова: синдром тиреотоксикоза; среди кардиологических больных; диффузный токсический зоб; иммунологический маркер; амиодарон-индуцированный тиреотоксикоз.

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KARDIOLOGIK BEMORLAR ORASIDA TIREOTOKSIKOZ SINDROMI KLINIK KECHISHINING O'ZIGA XOSLIGI

ANNOTATSIYA

Diffuz toksik bo'qoq – bu tireoid gormonlar ishlab chiqarilishining oshishi va qalqonsimon bezning diffuz kattalashishi bilan tavsiflanib, barcha autoimmun kasallik singari, nasliy oilaviy anamnezga ega bemorlarda tez-tez uchraydi, bu stress, chekish, infeksiya yod ta'siri va tug'ruqdan keyingi davr kabi atrof-muhit omillari, shuningdek birinchi navbatda qalqonsimon bezga ta'sir qiluvchi immunitetni tiklashga qaratilgan yuqori faollikdagi antivirus terapiyadan keyin yuzaga keladi. Tadqiqotning maqsadi kardiologik bemorlar orasidan diffuz toksik bo'qoqning ushrash sonini aniqlash va uning klinik kechishining xususiyatlarini baholashdan iborat. Material i uslublar. Klinik materiallar 2022 yil 6 oy davomida Orolbo'yi mintaqasi ixtisoslashtirilgan kardiologiya va kardiokirurgiya ilmiy-amaliy tibbiyot markazi poliklinikasida tekshiruv o'tkazilgan bemorlar orasidan to'plandi. Biz tomondan qalqonsimon bez kasalliklarini inkor qilish maqsadida kardiolog tomonidan yo'llanma berilgan 1150 bemorga tavsiya berildi. Natijalar. 1150 nafar bemordan 71 (6,2%) nafarida tireotoksikoz sindromi bilan kechuvchi kasalliklar aniqlandi. Gormonal va immunologik ma'lumotlar tahlili natijasida 24 (33,8%) nafar bemorda diffuz toksik bo'qoq tashxislandi. Diffuz toksik bo'qoq bilan ko'pgina bemorlar yurak – qon tomirining o'zgarishi tufayli kasallikning boshlanishida kardiologga murojaat qilishgan (birinchi aniqlangan diffuz toksik bo'qoq 37,5%).

Kalit so'zlar: tireotoksikoz sindromi; kardiologik bemorlar orasida; diffuz toksik bo'qoq; immunologik marker; amiodaron indutsirlangan tireotoksikoz.

Relevance of the study. Diffuse toxic goiter (DTG) is a disease that is characterized by increased production of thyroid hormones and diffuse enlargement of the thyroid gland, like all autoimmune diseases, it is more common in patients with a positive family history, and usually caused by environmental factors such as stress, smoking, infection, iodine exposure and the postpartum period, and after highly active antiretroviral therapy due to immune reconstitution, which primarily affects the thyroid gland [11]. It can also affect many other organs, including the heart, eyes, and skin.

This is the most common cause of hyperthyroidism [19], which accounts for 60% to 80% cases of hyperthyroidism. The effect of an excess of thyroid hormone in DTG leads to damage to almost all organs and, first of all, the cardiovascular system. Excess triiodothyronine

(FT3) and thyroxine (FT4) enhances metabolism in the body, catabolism of proteins and lipids. Patients with DTG complain of increased excitability, emotional lability, tearfulness, anxiety, sleep disturbance, drowsiness, impaired concentration, weakness, sweating, palpitations, trembling in the body, weight loss (Fig. 1) [2, 3, 6, 8].

Timely referral to thyroidectomy for DTG in dynamics leads to an improvement in the quality of life of patients. After thyroidectomy, all patients need to undergo hormonal examination for the purpose of timely hormone replacement therapy. Timely appointment of hormone replacement therapy with thyroid medications improves the quality of life and prevents the development of complications from various organs and systems [1].

Fig. 1. The thyroid gland is normal and with DTG

Under the influence of thyroid hormone, profound biochemical changes occur in the heart: hypoxia, a decrease in the content of glycogen, protein, Adenosine triphosphate, potassium content and an increase in sodium content. Cardiovascular disorders are characterized by tachycardia, which persists at rest and at night, as well as vascular dilatation, which, in combination with increased blood flow [4], determines the skin condition - warm to the touch and velvety. Increased contractility of the heart and vasodilation form a hyperkinetic type of

blood circulation: increased pulse pressure (due to an increase in systolic and a decrease in diastolic blood pressure), tachycardia, increased apex beat of the heart, pulsation of the vessels of the neck, thyroid region and epigastric region, an increased voltage of the teeth is noted on the ECG, with echocardiography – high ejection fraction and increased excursion of the heart walls [18].

Prolonged increased functional load on the heart under conditions of intensive metabolism in DTG leads to the development of dystrophic

changes in the myocardium with a subsequent decrease in exercise tolerance, the appearance of shortness of breath, and in severe cases, atrial fibrillation. Cardiovascular decompensation is more often observed in elderly patients, which is due to age-related changes in the heart muscle and the presence of concomitant cardiac pathology [2].

Changes that develop in the cardiovascular system under the influence of thyroid hormone (TH) can be the result of both their direct binding to cardiomyocyte receptors, and indirect influence through the activation of the sympathetic nervous system or through changes in the peripheral circulation. The release of cytokines, especially TNF- α , stimulated by TH, both directly and through activation of the renin-angiotensin-aldosterone system (RAAS), also affects the heart. At the same time, processes of apoptosis of cardiomyocytes develop and remodeling of the left ventricular myocardium with its diastolic dysfunction and a decrease in heart rate variability is formed, mainly due to indicators characterizing the activity of the parasympathetic division of the autonomic nervous system [14].

With DTG, dilatation of all chambers of the heart occurs, a moderate thickening of the walls of the left ventricle with an increase in myocardial mass. In patients with DTG, diastolic dysfunction of the left ventricle occurs mainly in the complicated form of the disease [2, 7].

Arterial hypertension (AH) is one of the most common manifestations of DTG. Its development is associated with an increase in cardiac output due to the direct effect of excess thyroid hormone on the myocardium, with a reflex response to increased metabolic demands, activation of the RAAS, and an increase in circulating blood volume [5]. It is traditionally believed that DTG is characterized by an increase in systolic blood pressure with normal or even reduced diastolic blood pressure, which leads to a significant increase in pulse pressure. An increase in pulse amplitude is a consequence of an increase in cardiac output and a decrease in total peripheral resistance in DTG [2]. It is highly likely that AH is one of the factors contributing to the development of pulmonary ventricular hypertrophy in DTG. In the absence of AH, only an eccentric variant of left ventricular hypertrophy develops, while in AH, concentric variants of pulmonary ventricular remodeling can also form, and their frequency increases significantly with as blood pressure increases [19].

It has been established that AH and DTG have a similar effect on the myocardium, but in patients with AH, in addition to changes in flow rates and their gradients, there is also an increase in the end-diastolic volume of the left ventricle, the lumen of the aortic root, and the size of the left atrium. In patients with DTG, an increase in stiffness and a decrease in the ability to relax the myocardium of the left ventricle were revealed. The severity of morphological and functional changes in the myocardium depended on the level of compensation of the thyroid status, however, complete clinical and laboratory compensation did not lead to a complete restoration of the state of the myocardium [9, 16].

Diagnosis of DTG begins with a thorough history and physical examination. History should include a family history of DTG [13].

Timely diagnosis of DTG is often difficult, which is associated with the nonspecific nature of the clinical picture. In the absence of treatment, the disease is accompanied by severe cardiovascular disorders, which can cause disability and death.

This research outlines modern ideas about the immunopathogenesis of the disease and its complications. Unlike other publications, here the mechanisms of development of clinical symptoms of DTG are considered, the age-related features of the course of the disease are analyzed, and the differential diagnosis of the disease is presented in a systematic way [19]. According to the summary data of foreign authors, along with the growth of endocrine diseases, there is an increase in the incidence of DTG. The total frequency of various diseases of the thyroid gland, even outside the zones of endemic goiter, is at least 20% of the total incidence. In goiter-endemic regions, this figure often exceeds 50% [15]. A number of scientific studies are being carried out in the world in order to develop and improve new methods for diagnosing and treating DTG. The typical course of DTG and the blurring of clinical symptoms often leads to late diagnosis and long-term, ineffective treatment of this pathology. Patients with overt thyrotoxicosis due to DTG should receive one of the following treatment options: radioactive iodine therapy (^{131}I), thyrostatic drugs, or thyroidectomy [10].

Treatment of DTG consists in the rapid relief of symptoms and a decrease in the secretion of thyroid hormones. A β -blocker should be given to symptomatic patients, especially those with a heart rate greater than 90 beats/min, patients with a history of cardiovascular disease, and elderly patients [17]. There are three options for reducing the synthesis of thyroid hormones. These options are: antithyroid drugs; radioiodine therapy; thyroidectomy. Therefore, the aim of the study is to determine the frequency of occurrence of diffuse toxic goiter among cardiac patients and to assess its clinical course.

Materials and methods

The collection of clinical material was carried out within 6 months, from January to July 2022, the collection of material was carried out in Cardiac Surgery of the Aral Sea Region. Patients asked for advice. Examination of patients was carried out jointly with the endocrinologist of the dispensary.

We consulted 1150 patients who were referred by cardiologists to rule out thyroid diseases. Of these, 993 (86.3%) women and 157 (13.7%) men aged 18 to 61 years. Among the examined patients, 71 patients (6.2%) were diagnosed with diseases occurring with thyrotoxicosis syndrome. The duration of thyrotoxicosis averaged 6.7 ± 2.5 years. When analyzing hormonal and immunological data, 24 (33.8%) patients were diagnosed with DTG, mixed toxic goiter in 11 (15.6%), toxic adenoma in 1 (0.14%), amiodarone-induced thyrotoxicosis in 7 (9.8%) patients, iatrogenic thyrotoxicosis in 5 (8.0%) patients, autoimmune thyroiditis (AITD) thyrotoxic phase in 23 (32.3%) patients. The remaining patients were diagnosed with various thyroid diseases. The data is presented in table 1.

Table 1

Distribution of examined patients

№	Nosology	Sex		Total
		Male	Female	
1	DTG	7	17	24
2	Thyrototoxic adenoma	-	1	1
3	Mixed toxic goiter	4	7	11
4	Amiodarone-induced thyrotoxicosis	6	1	7
5	Iatrogenic thyrotoxicosis	-	5	5
6	Autoimmune thyroiditis thyrotoxic phase	6	17	23
7	Endemic (diffuse) goiter 1-2 degree Euthyroidism	23	429	452
8	Diffuse goiter 3 degree Euthyroidism	23	261	284
9	Mixed goiter. Euthyroidism	-	56	56
10	Nodular goiter	8	40	48
11	Autoimmune thyroiditis. Euthyroidism	8	39	47

12	Pregnancy	-	16	16
13	Lactation	-	4	4
14	Healthy	72	100	172
	Total:	157	993	1150

Results and its discussion. DTG among patients with thyrotoxicosis syndrome was 33.8%. As can be seen from the table, the majority of patients are women (70.8%), which coincides with the literature data.

The main clinical symptoms of DTG were: palpitations in 100%, weight loss in 89%, bulging eyes in 54%, irritability in 85%, pain in the heart area in 50%, tremor in 85%, goiter in 96% of patients.

Among them, 9 (37.5%) had newly diagnosed DTG, the remaining patients received treatment with antithyroid drugs recommended by an

endocrinologist at the place of residence for an average of 5.4±2.7 years. The average dose of thiamazole was 15.3±7.8 mg/day. It was found that many patients did not regularly take antithyroid therapy, which led to decompensation and the appearance of the above symptoms. Taking into account the fact that the main symptoms were cardiac symptoms, the patients turned to a cardiologist in a cardiological dispensary.

The diagnosis of DTG was verified only on the basis of the immunological marker Anti-thyroid stimulating hormone receptor antibodies (TRAbs) along with TH and TSH.

Table 2

Indicators of hormonal background in DTG in the general group

	Control group (n=20)	Main group (n=24)
FT3, pg/ml	0,8±0,3	7,57±1,0*
FT4, pg/ml	14,2±0,9	28,45±7,40*
thyroid-stimulating hormone, mIU/ml	2,2±0,7	0,11±0,08*
Antibodies to thyroid-stimulating hormone receptors, ME/L	0,3±0,02	6,1±0,91*
Antibodies to thyroperoxidase, ME/L	20,6±3,4	73,3 ±11,3*

Note: n is the number of examined patients;

*-the presence of reliability in relation to the control (*p<0.0005)

As can be seen from Table 2, FT3 and FT4 were increased by 80% and 50% in patients%, accordingly. TSH was suppressed on average to 0.11±0.08 mIU/ml, TRAbs increased on average to 6.1±0.91 IU/l, which indicates the development of DTG. There is also an increase in antiTPO, which is often accompanied by DTG.

According to the results of the hormonal background, the patients were divided into 2 groups: with a manifest form of thyrotoxicosis in 7 patients (29.2%) and a subclinical form in 17 patients (70.8%). The

indicators of the hormonal background in manifest thyrotoxicosis were as follows - the levels of FT3 and FT4 were 6.93±1.0 pg/ml and 28.0±7.3 pg/ml, respectively, and the level of TSH was significantly reduced relative to the control and amounted to 0.15±0.72 pg/ml, with subclinical thyrotoxicosis FT3 and FT4 were 3.54±0.29 pg/ml.ml and 16.1±3.0 pg/ml, the level of TSH was significantly reduced and amounted to 0.13±0.07 mIU/ml. The TRAbs level was 3.67±0.51 IU/l for subclinical thyrotoxicosis, and 7.4±1.23 IU/l for manifest thyrotoxicosis. The levels of anti-TPO indicators were 69.1±10.2 and 79.3±12.3 IU/l, respectively (Table 3).

Table 3

Indicators of the hormonal background in DTG in the general group

	Control group (n=20)	Subclinical thyrotoxicosis (n=7)	Manifest thyrotoxicosis (n=17)
FT3, pg/ml	0,8±0,3	3,54±0,29*	6,93±1,0*,**
FT4, pg/ml	14,2±0,9	16,1±3,0	28,0±7,3*,**
thyroid-stimulating hormone, mIU/ml	2,2±0,7	0,13±0,07*	0,15±0,72*
Antibodies to thyroid-stimulating hormone receptors, ME/L	0,3±0,02	3,67±0,51 **	7,4±1,23 *,**
Antibodies to thyroperoxidase, ME/L	20,6±3,4	69,1 ±10,2 *	79,3±12,3*

Note: n is the number of examined patients;

*-the presence of reliability in relation to the control (*p<0.0005)

-the presence of reliability in relation to the studied groups (p<0.005)

Table 4

The volume of the thyroid gland in the studied patients

	Control n=20	Males n=6	Females n=18
Volume of the thyroid, ml	16,47±4,7	37,9±4,0*	30,3±7,3*

Note. Significance of difference to kg: * P<0.05 in relation to kg

As can be seen from Table 4, in patients with DTG, the thyroid gland is increased in both men and women in relation to the control.

In 1 patient, thyrotoxic adenoma was detected according to clinical, instrumental, hormonal data, as well as thyroid scintigraphy, which was performed at the RSSPMC of Endocrinology. The patient was

prescribed antithyroid therapy, so thiamazole was prescribed at a dose of 30 mg / day, β-blockers, sedatives were also prescribed, and the patient was referred to a surgeon for a radical solution to this problem, thyroidectomy.

When analyzing the anamnesis of patients with amiodarone-induced thyrotoxicosis, it was found that all patients, for an average of 3.4 ± 1.0 years, take amiodarone at an average dose of 350.6 ± 23.8 mg/day according to the recommendations of a cardiologist. The drug was prescribed for the purpose of antiarrhythmic therapy, without previously examining the structural and functional state of the thyroid gland. Patients noted the appearance and increase in symptoms of hyperthyroidism with prolonged use, more than 3 years, of amiodarone. It is known that the development of amiodarone-induced thyrotoxicosis depends not only on the dose, but also on the duration of taking amiodarone. Patients noted that many symptoms appeared while taking amiodarone. amiodarone-induced thyrotoxicosis often develops in iodine-deficient regions. There are type 1 amiodarone-induced thyrotoxicosis and type 2 amiodarone-induced thyrotoxicosis (destructive thyroiditis).

Due to the increased mortality and severity of the course, patients with amiodarone-induced thyrotoxicosis should be considered as emergency, especially the elderly and/or patients with reduced left ventricular function. Total thyroidectomy is recommended in patients with amiodarone-induced thyrotoxicosis, impaired cardiac function or severe preexisting cardiac disease, and in patients whose thyrotoxicosis is resistant to therapy. This decision is made by a multidisciplinary team consisting of an endocrinologist, a cardiologist, an anesthesiologist and a surgeon with extensive experience in thyroid surgery.

Amiodarone should be continued in life-threatening arrhythmias and in critically ill patients with a poor prognosis; in patients with amiodarone-induced thyrotoxicosis 2 for non-life-threatening arrhythmias, the drug can be continued, but this may be associated with a prolongation of the period required to achieve euthyroidism and, possibly, a high risk of relapse. The decision to continue or withhold amiodarone should be individualized based on cardiac risk stratification and made jointly by the cardiologist and endocrinologist.

Antithyroid drugs for the treatment of most cases of amiodarone-induced thyrotoxicosis 1. Due to the fact that the iodine-loaded thyroid gland is resistant to antithyroid drugs, the use of a 4-6 week course of sodium perchlorate at doses not exceeding 1 g / day may be useful in accelerating the control of hyperthyroidism.

Oral glucocorticoids are recommended as the first line of treatment for amiodarone-induced thyrotoxicosis 2 with moderate thyrotoxicosis. The decision to treat mild or subclinical forms should be made taking into account the state of the cardiovascular system in close contact with the cardiologist.

In patients with amiodarone-induced thyrotoxicosis 2 with a critical course, thyroidectomy can be performed for health reasons. Life-saving thyroidectomy may be considered in patients with amiodarone-induced thyrotoxicosis 1 and mixed/indeterminate forms.

Table 5

Indicators of the hormonal background amiodarone-induced thyrotoxicosis

	Controlling group (n=20)	Subclinical thyrotoxicosis (n=3)	Manifest thyrotoxicosis (n=4)
FT3, pg/ml	0,8±0,3	3,87±0,34	7,80±0,33*
FT4, pg/ml	14,2±0,9	14,3±3,9	29,9±4,9*
thyroid-stimulating hormone, mIU/ml	2,2±0,7	0,14±0,06*	0,13±0,07*
Antibodies to thyroid- stimulating hormone receptors, ME/L	0,3±0,02	0,8±0,14**	0,7±0,78*
Antibodies to thyroperoxidase, ME/L	20,6±3,4	52,3 ±7,1*	68,7±8,7*

Note: n is the number of examined patients;

-the presence of reliability in relation to the control ($p < 0.0005$)

As can be seen from Table 5, in patients of this group, the content of TRAbs is within normal values, while the content of Antibodies to thyroperoxidase in both groups is above normal values. Timely diagnosis of thyroid diseases in cardiac patients will help prevent the development of amiodarone-induced thyrotoxicosis or other autoimmune thyroid diseases.

Ultrasound of the thyroid gland in patients with amiodarone-induced thyrotoxicosis gives us grounds to make a diagnosis of AITD, since all the examined patients had an echocardiography of chronic thyroiditis with echo inhomogeneity, alternation of hypo- and hyperechoic areas, as well as areas of fibrosis, pseudonodes, with increased blood flow during the study of vascularization.

Analysis of data from patients with iatrogenic thyrotoxicosis showed that all women (100%) took thyroid drugs in combination with an iodine preparation for a long time. Thus, the average dose of levothyroxine was 105.8 ± 28.9 µg/day, and potassium iodide 148.4 ± 22.6 µg/day (100-200 µg). When analyzing the data of ultrasound of the thyroid gland of these women, it was revealed that before taking the drugs, 2 women had a nodular goiter, and 3 had an echocardiography of a diffuse goiter. According to the words, after undergoing ultrasound of the thyroid gland, women, without previously examining the thyroid status, were prescribed the above therapy.

When examining the hormonal background in 1 woman, TSH was within the low limit of the norm, although there were all the symptoms of thyrotoxicosis, in 4 women TSH was suppressed to an average of 0.14 ± 0.08 mIU/ml, the content of immunological markers - Antibodies to thyroperoxidase and TRAbs were in within the normal range.

All patients with DTG underwent ultrasound of the thyroid gland, which clearly showed a decrease in the echogenicity of the thyroid tissue

and an increase in volume. The average thyroid volume was 36.8 ± 12.3 ml in women and 56.9 ± 13.1 ml in men.

Thus, it turned out that many patients with DTG due to Heart vascular insufficiency turn to cardiologists at the onset of the disease (37.5% of newly diagnosed DTG). To rule out thyrotoxicosis syndrome, cardiologists send these patients for a consultation with endocrinologists. Out of 1150 patients, 71 patients (6.2%) had diseases occurring with thyrotoxicosis syndrome. When analyzing hormonal and immunological data, DTG was diagnosed in 24 (33.8%) patients. The majority of patients are women - 70.8%.

Approximately 15-20% of amiodarone-treated patients develop thyrotoxicosis (amiodarone-induced thyrotoxicosis, AITD) or hypothyroidism (amiodarone-induced hypothyroidism, AIH). Amiodarone-induced thyrotoxicosis type 1 or 2 is differentiated using color Doppler ultrasound. The choice of treatment method depends on this.

Amiodarone should be continued in life-threatening arrhythmias and in critically ill patients with a poor prognosis; in patients with amiodarone-induced thyrotoxicosis 2 with non-life-threatening arrhythmias, the drug can be continued, but this may be associated with a prolongation of the period required to achieve euthyroidism and, possibly, a high risk of relapse. The decision to continue or withhold amiodarone should be individualized based on cardiac risk stratification and made jointly by the cardiologist and endocrinologist.

Also, patients with amiodarone-induced thyrotoxicosis were diagnosed, with an average intake of amiodarone at an average dose of 350.6 ± 23.8 mg/day according to the recommendations of a cardiologist. The drug was prescribed for the purpose of antiarrhythmic therapy, without previously examining the structural and functional state of the thyroid gland. Also, during the examination, patients with iatrogenic

thyrotoxicosis were diagnosed, and all women (100%) who took thyroid drugs in combination with an iodine preparation for a long time.

When analyzing the data of ultrasound of the thyroid gland of these women, it was revealed that before taking the drugs, 2 women had a nodular goiter, and 3 had an echocardiography of a diffuse goiter. According to the words, after undergoing ultrasound of the thyroid gland, women, without previously examining the thyroid status, were prescribed the above therapy.

Among cardiac patients in the presence of tachycardia, irritability, weight loss, sweating, tremor of the fingers, especially in elderly patients, it is necessary to exclude thyrotoxicosis syndrome with the determination of TSH, FT4, total T3, TRAbs [12].

Conclusions

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ЖУРНАЛ РЕПРОДУКТИВНОГО ЗДОРОВЬЯ И УРО-НЕФРОЛОГИЧЕСКИХ ИССЛЕДОВАНИЙ

TOM 4, NOMER 4

**JOURNAL OF REPRODUCTIVE HEALTH AND
URO-NEPHROLOGY RESEARCH**

VOLUME 4, ISSUE 4

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